

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Murodova Madinabonu

ADABIYOT DARSLARINI O'ZLASHTIRISHDA BADIY MATNNING AHAMIYATI VA

DOLZARBLIGI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

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